

An analysis of metadiscourse strategies on selected letters of appeal to students’ disciplinary committee in a University in Ogun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Metadiscourse strategies in letters of appeals have the potentials of either allowing or denying students the opportunity to be given leniencies depending on how they are structured and used. This study investigates metadiscourse strategies in letters of appeal written to Students’ Disciplinary Committee by students, their parents or their guardians. Five (5) letters of appeal were purposively selected from the corpus of letters of appeal sent to the Students’ Disciplinary Committee (SDC) of Mountain Top University, Ogun State, Nigeria. This study adopts Sherif and Hovland (1961)’s Social Judgmental Theory and Hyland’s (2005) Interpersonal Model of Metadiscourse for data analysis. One of the major findings is that misuse of metadiscourse (especially attitude markers) rubs students the opportunity of being granted leniency where they would have been given such. The study, therefore, recommends that letters of appeal should not be written in a hurry; rather, writers should understand the components of the said letters before they present them for SDC’s consideration. Again, organizational policies of individual institutions should be understood by the writers of these letters. Writers are equally expected to understand how these letters should be written before they meticulously write and send them to SDC.

Keywords

Metadiscourse strategies, letters of appeal, leniency, writers, Interpersonal model

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Introduction

Metadiscourse, is a vastly used multidiscipline concept (Amiryousefi, 2010, Gbolami, et al 2014; Pandey 2020) “in current discourse analysis and language teaching” (Hyland 2017: 16). According to Hyland (2005:16 as cited in Adel & Mauranen 2011), metadiscourse first appeared in Applied Linguistics. It was first introduced by Zelling Harris in 1959 (Gbolami 2014) and became popular in Applied linguistics of mid 1980 in the work of vande kopple, Crismore 1989 and Williams (1981). Adel & Mauranen (2010) further maintain that metadiscourse focuses on “discourse about discourse” of academic texts of various types; the “discourse beyond discourse” or “talk about talk” (Gbolami et al 2014; Nordquist 2018). It is defined both as a “textual interaction” otherwise termed integrative (Mauranen 1993) and as a “reflexivity” also known as “non-integrative or reflexive model” (Adel). Metadiscourse considers verbal messages as not just means of communication but as “social acts which involve the writers, readers, speakers and listeners interacting with” one another so as to “effect the ways ideas are presented and understood” (Armiryousefi and Rasekh 2010). It centres on the relationship between the “writers of the texts and their texts” and “texts authors and their readers” (Hyland 2005 as cited in Mirshami & Allami 2013). It is a vital “linguistic resource that binds different parts of a text together and facilitates communication” (Panday 2020: 1) while building relations with the readers or the listeners.

Metadiscourse is suitable in analyzing discourse of all sorts. It can be formally or informally used in everyday conversations to perform various functions. In other words, metadiscourse focuses on discourse above discourse (Nordquist, Adel & Mauranen) of various forms. The heterogeneity of metadiscourse informs it different uses such as how to show attitudes, tie text together, direct audience on what to do with lexical items, etc. A whole text from any discipline, for example, can be analysed under metadiscourse. All human activities that involve language use (verbally and non-verbally) inform functional, structural, social constructionist, and many other aspects of metadiscourse uses. Its vastness and use enable researchers to carry out studies on metadiscourse features in many languages and forms (Hyland, et al 2021).

Different scholars (such as Jensen 2009; Karimi, & Asadnia, 2014; Burneikaitè, 2008; Musa et al, 2019 , Abdollahzadeh 2011; Hyland 2005; Perez, Llantada 2006, Luukka, 1994; Kopple, 1985, 1988; Crisome, 1989, Mauranen 1993, 2001; Adel 2006; 2010) have researched into the field of metadiscourse and had come out with varying outcomes. In other words there is no harmony in the results of researches in the area of metadiscourse (Adel, 2006). Considering the fields of researchers’ interest in metadiscourse research, Kopple (2012) opines that scholars from discourse analysis, linguistics, applied linguistics, pragmatics, rhetoric, and second language theory and pedagogy are those involved in the study of metadiscourse. Despite the fact that metadiscourse involved researchers from different field, Adel (2010 as cited in Mauranen 1993 and Adel 2006) submits that there are only two different strands of metadiscourse that are discernible; the one that adopts a narrow definition (a reflexive model) and the other that adopts a broad definition (i.e. the interactive model).

It worth stating that metadiscourse has various strategies depending on its contexts and operations. Some scholars explain metadiscourse generally to include markers or strategies while other explain it holistically as strategies. In other words, situations and use determine how metadiscourse and its makers are applied. Some of these discourse strategies are assigned to its structural nature, some to functional use and other to any other use. Metadiscourse strategies or markers could be face-strategies if they conversational, text strategies, if they are based on text or sign and semiotic strategies if they focused on non-verbal symbols.

Researchers had emerged with some metadiscourse strategies; some of which are: Kopple (2012) who, identifies six taxonomies of metadiscourse such as text connectives, (such as *first, next, in the third place*), code glosses (1958) (such as *so-called or what some people call*); illocution markers (such as *I hypothesize that, to sum up, we calm that , I promise to, and for example*), epistemology markers (such as *it is possible that, perhaps, most certainly*), attitude markers (such as *fortunately, I regret, I rejoice, I am grateful that*) and commentary (Kopple 2002) such as some of you will be amazed that; and Hyland (2005) who identifies two broad types, interactive and interactional; these are with ten subcategories, five for each subdivision.

Although many scholars (such as Crismore et al, 1993, Kopple 1985, Hyland, 2005, Adel 2006) had come up with various metadiscourse taxonomies, this study adopts Hyland’s (2005)’s Interpersonal metadiscourse model of interactive and interactional paradigms (which relies on taxonomies. The interactive and interactional taxonomies are further grouped into sub-strategies of transitions, endophoric markers, frame markers, evidential, code glosses, hedges, attitude markers, boosters, engagements markers and self-mentions (Mirshamis & Allami 2010, Gbolami 2014, Adel 2006, Musa 2019)) to analyse excerpts from letters of appeal sent to the SDC of MTU.

Letters of appeals seek to plead for leniency from judges or *To Whom It May Concern* to reduce or remove punishments meant for violators of organisational rules and regulations. Everyone writes a letter of appeal when necessary; but it is often regrettable to know that these letters do not meet the purposes in which they are meant for. In other words, it is not all letters of appeals that are capable of performing the functions in which they are meant for. As a member of SDC in MTU, I have witnessed cases where pardons are either delayed or denied due to the fact that the writers do not understand how to write letters of appeal; or know the necessary components of letters of appeal to SDC. There are also instances where letters of appeal meet it demands due to the metadiscourse strategies applied in such letters. This research therefore acts as a resource material for those who write or intend to write letters of appeal to utilise it so as to obtain their intended demands.

The present research therefore investigates metadiscourse strategies employed in letters of appeals sent to SDC in Mountain Top University (MTU), a private university owned by Mountain of Fire and Miracles Ministries, located in Prayer-City, Mowe, Ibafo, Ogun State, Nigeria. This study fills an existing gap in literature by investigating metadiscourse strategies in letters of appeal using not only the popular or predominantly used Hyland’s (2005) Interpersonal Metadiscourse taxonomies but Sherif and Hovland (1961)’s Social Judgmental Theory. To the best of the researcher’s knowledge, no work has successful

carried out an analytical investigation of this sort where letters of appeal are analysed using combinatory models in question.

The main aim of this study is to investigate the metadiscourse strategies used in letters of appeals to SDC in MTU. The objectives of this study are to identify discourse strategies predominantly used in letters of appeal; to examine the functions of metadiscourse strategies in letters of appeal and to suggest metadiscourse strategies that are capable of evoking the latitude of acceptance thereby eliciting leniency, pardons or reduction in punishments for the offenders.

1. Discourse

Discourse is a multidiscipline concept (Sharma & Sharma, 2010; McCarthy, 2014,) that originates from a Latin word, “discursus.” Many disciplines such as psychology, sociology, anthropology, ecology, physiology, etc. are equally engaged in the study of discourse. It is a speech considered as purposeful social action. Each context defines its discourse differently. It is any form of language above the sentence and language use.

2. Discourse Analysis

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Discourse Analysis (hence DA) is an interdisciplinary theory. McCarthy et al (2014) observe that it is a wide-ranging and heterogeneous discipline which finds its unity in the description of language above the sentence and an interest in the contexts and cultural influences which affect language use”(7). It is the study of “language and the contexts in which it is used” (5). It uses naturally occurring, authentic language data (He, 2017). One of the ways to analyse discourse is to use DA.

2.1. Discourse strategies

Discourse strategies are the techniques that language users employ in spoken, written or non-verbal communication to organise, order, change, show, announce, express, what we write and say and carry out other activities both formally or informally. Prihodko et al 2020 observe that they are “the application of global properties of discourse, correlated with its status as an integral communicative-cognitive means” (3). It is generally defined as markers for communication between or among people (Walker, 1994 as cited in Shartiely 2013). They are techniques employed by discourse participants during “their conversation” and during their “attempt to understand each other in that particular context of the conversation.” (Gumperz 1981).

2.2. METADISOURSE

Metadiscourse is a polymorphous concept (according to Musa et al 2019: 20, it is a fuzzy concept) that speakers and writers used to make directions and purposes of a text

(Nordquist 2018). It is derived from two Greek words, “beyond” and “discourse” which means discourse about discourse (Nordquist); and was coined by Zelling S. Harris in 1959 (Gbolami et al 2014). It is an important field of enquiry that focuses on “organizing and producing persuasive writing” (Rasekh 2010:159). According to Hyland (2017), metadiscourse means how we use language out of consideration for the readers or hearers based on our estimation of how best we can help people process and comprehension what we say (17). According to (Williams 1981 and Kopple 1985 as cited in Musa 2019), metadiscourse is a “non-propositional aspect of discourse that does not add to the content but guides the reader to interpret text and expresses stance towards the content and the readers” (Musa et al 2019:20).

Metadiscourse aligns with Hallidayan formulation of his ideational, textual and interpersonal metafunctions. Metadiscourse is grouped as textual and interpersonal aspects of discourse as regards to the William (1981) and Kopple (1985)’s definition. It is a “pragmatic use of language to comment reflexively on discourse” (Gbolami et al 2014). They are text elements that “comment about the main information of a text, but which themselves contain only inessential information” (Hui & Na, 2008). It is used now-a-days in analyzing both spoken and written language.

2.3. Metadiscourse Strategies

Metadiscourse strategies are linguistic markers that communicate the semantic content of the writers/speakers to the readers /listeners. According to (Sukma, (2017), metadiscourse are “persuasive strategies” use in communication between the senders and the receivers. This is different from discourse strategies which is devoid of persuasive aspects. Kuswoyo & Siregar observe that metadiscourse makers are forms that make up textual and interpersonal relations. They are the linguistics elements that take into consideration, the interpersonal, textual and ideational metafunctions; they are the interactive and interactional linguistic (Thompson 2001) elements that are applied in both texts and speeches. Metadiscourse strategies or metadiscourse markers are techniques that are used to link words or phrases in spoken or written discourse. These are linguistics signposts that enable speakers/writers to decipher meanings in both texts and contexts.

There are structural discourse strategies, functional discourse strategies; propositional discourse strategies (repetition, questioning and cod-switching, connectivity discourse markers (so and now) and contextual personal markers (pronouns you, we and I) and other types of strategies. Any linguistic marker or technique that assist the writers / speakers to effectively send their texts/speeches and the readers/listeners to easily understand discourses above discourses is a metadiscourse strategy; this includes all discourse strategies, persuasive words and expressions employed in “talk about talk”.

2.4. Appeal letters and types

Letters are official functional messages sent to recipients who are expected to give either immediate or distant feedback. There are numerous official letters such as letter of enquiry, letter of complaints, letter of admission and letter of appeal. An appeal letter is a serious formal letter sent to a higher authority demanding for a “change in decision”

(Ferreira 2020). There are emotional appeal letter, personal appeal letters, group appeal letter, family appeal letter, etc. Emotional appeals seek to plead for cases based on special circumstances such as appeal letters sent to SDC of any institution.

A letter of appeal to SDC should include some or all the elements below.

- i. A demonstration of understanding of the organizational policy
- ii. A knowledge of the receiver
- iii. A list of arguments in favour of the appeal
- iv. A request of the review of the decision taken by the higher authority
- v. A description of the demand outcome and;
- vi. A follow-up (career karma)

2.5. Social Judgment Theory

Social Judgment Theory (SJT) was propounded by Muzafer Sherif, Carolyn Sherif and Carl Hovland in 1961. It is the scientific theory that is based on epistemological, ontological and axiological premises. Sherif, Sherif & Hovland observe that epistemologically, there is a universal truth that individuals judge messages that they receive. Ontologically, SJT is based on the fact that people's behaviours "can be predicted"; and axiologically, it is a "value neutral because theoretical propositions are objective and not biased" (Sherif, Sherif & Hovland).

This theory focuses on the fact that people assess or judge others due to the content of messages based on their anchors, or stance, on a particular topic message (Sherif, Sherif & Hovland, 1961). Besides individual's anchor, every person's attitude is judged based on three latitudes namely, the latitude of acceptance, the latitude of rejection and the latitude of noncommitment. According to (Sherif & Hovland 1961):

the latitude of acceptance, ...includes all those ideas that a person finds acceptable.
...the latitude of rejection ...includes all those ideas that a person finds unacceptable.
... the latitude of noncommitment, ...includes ideas for which you have no opinion—
you neither accept nor reject these ideas (105).

From the foregoing, individuals may decide to accept, reject or be undecided about the specific messages and attitudes that they have received. People's reflection on attitudes and messages evoke their decisions, opinions and decisions.

2.6. Hyland's (2005) Interpersonal Model of Metadiscourse

Hyland's (2005) Interpersonal Metadiscourse markers have two major categories: the interactive and interactional metadiscourses. The interactive metadiscourse focuses on "ways of organizing discourse" to "reflect the writer's assessment of what need to be made explicit to guide what should be recovered from the text" (Hyland & Jiang 2018: 4) while the former concentrates on the "writer's efforts to control the level of personality in text" and his/ her ability to "establish a suitable relationship to his or her data, arguments and audience" (4). The writer is equally expected to be intimate with the reader and this can be replicated through his "expression of attitude and commitments" (4).

The subcategories of Hyland’s interpersonal metadiscourse are “transitions, endophoric markers, frame markers, evidential, code glosses, hedges, attitude markers, boosters, engagements markers and self-mentions” (Massaabi 2014; Khedri et al 2014; Lawal 2018: 2, Abdi, 2010). Transitions are conjunctions used “to mark additive, constrastive and consequential steps in discourse” (Hyland 2005 as cited in Lawal, 2). Boroujeni (2012 as cited by Lawal) calls transitions text connectives. These are classified as consequences, reminders and topicalisers.

Frame-makers are text boundaries employed to indicate items that mark the beginning of one’s stage to another. It shows boundary topic shifts and announces discourse goals. They are the overt organising linguistic features that are employed to reduce processing load (Abdi, et al 2010). Endophoric markers are extra-textual information that point the reader to what has been said earlier. Evidentials are referential; exophoric information are (information outside the text) information that point to the source of the text. Code glosses are used to expatiate points already stated or expressed by the speaker or writer. Hyland (2005) classifies the above under interactive metadiscourse.

Under transactional metadiscourse, he grouped, hedges, boosters, attitude markers, self mentions and engagement markers. Hedges are employed to show probability; boosters are used to project clarity; attitude markers express the attitude of the writers or speakers through their tones. Self-mentions are inclusions and references to the writers through the use of personal pronouns such as I, we, us, ours, etc; and engagement markers establish the relationship between the writers/ speakers and the readers/listeners. The aforementioned taxonomies (i.e. Hyland (2005)’ Interpersonal Metadiscourse Model) are tabularized below as follows:

S/N	Taxonomy	Meanings	Examples
Interactive Metadiscourse			
1.	Transitions	To mark our boundaries relations between words	And, but this, in addition, furthermore, more so,
2.	Frame markers	Discourse acts to indicate sequences.	First, second, firstly, secondly, to conclude,
3.	Endophoric makers	Pre and post- information from other parts of the texts.	As noted before or below, see page three, chapter 4, as earlier stated etc.
4.	Evidentials	Information outside the texts that points to the texts at hand.	Accordingly to Anana 2022, as stated by Ayodele, etc.
5.	Code glosses		Such as, in other words, namely
Transactional Metadiscourse			
6.	Hedges	These are modals used in transacting discourses	Should, may, ought to have, dare to, can, etc.
7.	Boosters	These are emphasizeers that establish the certainty of discourse	To be frank, surely, definitely , clearly, etc.

S/N	Taxonomy	Meanings	Examples
8.	Attitude markers	These are expressions of the writers or speakers' attitudes towards propositions.	Surprisingly, unbelievably, unfortunately, regrettably, etc.
9.	Self mentions	Inclusion of first persons' personal pronouns in discourses	We, I, mine, ours, my, etc.
10.	Engagement markers	These devices enable the writer to have close relationship with the reader.	Note this, consider that, see this, take that, etc.

(Examples modified by the author)

3. Methodology

This is a qualitative research; this work adopts an ex post facto research design: data were not manipulated but retrieved as they were already in existent. The researcher conveniently selected five letters from the corpus of letters she received from SDC of Mountain Top University, where she is a member. Excerpts or data were randomly collected, presented and analysed using Sherif, Sherif & Hovland (1961)'s Social Judgment Theory (SJT) and Hyland (2005) Interpersonal Metadiscourse Model.

3.1. Data presentation and Analysis

Five (5) letters were randomly selected from many letters of appeal sent to SDC by students, parents and guidance of students who were either rusticated or expelled from the university due to various decrees of their major violation of the university's rules and regulations. Students, their parents and guidance, do not always appeal for minor offences that attract less stringent punishment but serious cases. Excerpts of letters are first presented (in italics) in paragraph as Para 1 (or Paras 1 and 2) to the end accordingly before their analysis; again, each letter of appeal is abbreviated as LoA 1 to the end appropriately.

3.2. Data Presentation 1: Excerpt from LoA 1

3.2.1. Para 1 of LoA 1

I ... from ... department, Mountain Top University with the Matric no... hereby write to apologize for my bad behaviour regarding the increase in school fees. I'm sorry for making the seemingly viral video that was posted across social media platforms, asking you, the Chancellor to come to the aid of the students as the hike in school fees was rather too sudden.

3.2.2. Analysis of Para 1 of LoA 1

The first paragraph opens with a self mention with remorseful lexical items such as "I. *apologize, I'm sorry,*"; these may evoke the emotions of the reader or listener to pity

as the sender is apologetic for the offence(s) he committed. These metadiscourse features indicate the writer’s admission to the offence he is asking SDC to reconsider for reduction, forgiveness or/and pardon.

It also includes engagement marker. The inclusion of an engagement maker “that was posted” further clarifies the message; but seems to make the writer distant from the offence committed so far. It would have been fully apologetic if he has completely shown his involvement by using a direct speech here (such as “that I posted). Here, it seems as if it were another person that posted the viral video.

3.2.3. Para 2 of LoA 1

I am also really sorry for any way the video could have sabotaged the image of the school as it wasn’t intended to do that, it was only a cry for help that you do something about the situation, absolutely harmless.

3.2.4. Analysis of Para 2 of LoA 1

Paragraph 2 starts with self mention (*I am*), but followed by self defence, “*it wasn’t intended to do that, it was only a cry for help*” This appears to negate his early seemingly self involvement and plea. One’s previous plea which necessitated the unfavourable decision by the Committee may be misconstrued by this kind of “self defence;” and may evoke a rejection of the almost persuasive tendencies rendered by self-mentions and apologetic items earlier stated.

3.3. Para 3 of LoA 1

I would like to add that I faced the Student’s Disciplinary Counsel Panel regarding this on the first of November 2021, and could be on my way out of the school for good. Please sir, I would really like that you help me as I am going through series of challenges presently and being expelled would only compound it.

3.3.1. Analysis of Para 3 of LoA 1

Paragraph 3 also opens with a self mention, “*I*” (with a hedge “*would*”), and in the middle, again, “*I faced*”, “*I*” accompanied by a hedge “*would*”. Although this is explanatory, it is unnecessary; it should be noted that it is the same Committee that disciplined the writer that the letter of appeal is sent to. Again, whatever the offender goes through as a result of the punishment he undergoes, is not necessary here, because anything unpalatable normally results in emotional traumas to a number of people who cannot manage theirs.

Again, the engagement marker “*this*” is referring to the Panel that the writer faced on November 2021. Although, this seems to show the psychological traumas that the writer might have undergone since the inception of the problem in questions; it appears not to influence the latitude of acceptance by the Committee.

3.4. Para 4 of LoA 1

I am really sorry, sir, and I hope that you'll consider my appeal and receive a favorable answer.

3.4.1. Analysis of Para 4 of LoA 1

Here, the inclusion of self-mentions accompanied by persuasive and optimistic lexis (“*I am really sorry;*” “*I hope that ...*”) are capable of inducing pity and making the Committee to lessen the punishment of the offender. These self-involvements and independence strategies (Jones 25) as located almost near the concluding paragraph of this letter, is capable of negating the aforementioned self-defense and rendering it null and void. It is also capable of generating arguments on whether or not the plea should be accepted or rejected by members of SDC. A letter of appeal should not take serious time from members of any higher authority to decide unanimously what latitude of judgment to take.

3.5. Para 5 of LoA 1

In addition, I would love, so much to meet with the Chancellor for prayers.

3.5.1. Analysis of Para 5 of LoA 1

This paragraph seems to be unnecessary here because the letter is not directed to the Chancellor of the University, why then the inclusion of inappropriate such an extraneous material in this letter. The possibility of misinterpreting this statement is obvious. It could be argued that the writer wants to inform the Committee that he has access to the Chancellor who through his prayers may influence the verdict of the Committee. It could also connote that the writer expects the Committee to help him get in contact with the Chancellor. Whatever way, no aspect of any letter of appeal should be ambiguous and subsequently generating various interpretations.

3.6. Data Presentation 2: LoA 2

3.6.1. Para1of LoA 2

We the parent of the above-named students hereby write to beg for leniency on the punishment meted on our child for the offence he committed, being a first offender.

3.6.2. Data Analysis of Para1 of LoA 2

This appeal letter opens with self-involvement “*we...*” followed by an endophoric matter “*the above-named student,*” a transition, “*hereby*” and a persuasive self-involvement feature “*write to beg for leniency*”; but it lacks its basic components of explaining and admitting to the offence committed by the offender. Besides these, this letter is extremely short and lacks concreteness (that it is expected to contain). Rather than identifying the offence that the son committed before pleading for leniency, the parent only points to the Committee to consider the offender as the first timer.

The phrase “*being a first offender*” appears to suggest to the Committee to give a fair judgment to the offender irrespective of the type of offence he committed. This is a covert defence, attempting to cover up the offence. This stance may not enable the Committee to offer the desired intention of the writer.

3.6.3. Para 2 of LoA 2

He is remorseful and we promise that he would hence forth be of good behaviour and such would not be repeated.

3.6.4. Data Analysis of Para 2 of LoA2

This second paragraph is very vague and lacks its solidness/concreteness. After just presenting to the Committee that the son in question is a first offender, the writer further stated that the son is remorseful and promises to be of good behaviour; and would not repeat the offence any longer. How are the members of the committee expected to know these when there is no evidence to prove the truthfulness of the expressions. These expressions cannot affect the decision of the committee positively; rather, it may lead to the rejection of the appeal; since there is no sincerity and proof of honesty of the statement. Besides, one’s remorsefulness and promises to renounce bad behaviours do not nullify the judgment for any offence that one commits.

3.7. Para 3 of LoA 2

*We pray that our plead would meet the mercy of **Christ** in your heart, while we await your favourable response.*

3.7.1. Data Analysis of Para 3 of LoA 2

Again this paragraph opens with a self-mention; but seems to be misdirected, as the writer cannot attest to the fact that there is mercy of Christ in the hearts of the Committee members. Also, it is not certain that the “pseudo appeal letter” will change the decision of the Committee in a positive direction of choosing the latitude of acceptance.

3.7.2. Data Presentation 3: LoA 3

3.7.3 Para1 of LoA 3

I ... hereby write of my son... who was alledged of stolen and was rusticated from the university for two semesters.

3.7.4 Data Analysis of Para 1 of LoA 3

Although this letter opens with self-involvement, (*I*) and a booster (hereby), the writer is not yet convinced that her son committed the offence. The expression “who *was alledged of stolen*” is quite ambiguous and confusing; and is capable of affecting the judgment

negatively. This shows the writer's distance from the offence that her son committed. She has not admitted that her son actually stole and deserves to be rusticated for two semesters.

From the opening of the above letter, the inclusion of ungrammaticality shows that the letter was not given its attention or that it was written in a hurry. A letter of this magnitude desires time, carefulness and technical knowhow of how it is written.

3.8. Para 2 of LoA 3

I plead for pardon and that the University reviews of the punishment meted out to him and consider a period of deliverance for him at the Centre for New Life to enable him overcome his challenges. On our part, we will counsel him and also support him in every area to enable him align himself on the path of honour and integrity.

3.8.1. Data Analysis of Para 2 of LoA 3

Again, the paragraph opens with a self-mention and a persuasive statement (*I plead for pardon...*). This might have evoked the pity of the Committee into action of choosing the latitude of acceptance of the plea; but the next transitive statement (through a connective); *...and consider a period of deliverance...* evokes mixed feelings among the SDC members and is capable of exposing them to the latitude of rejection ; which may not augur well with what the letter is intended to do.

Also, the writer's suggestions to the Committee imply that she is partially familiar with the institution's policy on the issue of theft (which is a grave misconduct in MTU). These extraneous suggestions are not necessary; because rather than meeting their desired goals, they are irrelevant, provocative and suggestive, showing that the Committee did not know what to do initially before the said student was rusticated.

Again, this letter is very brief and probably, that is why it is not able to include relevant components of an appeal letter (such as a writers' explicit explanation of offence committed or alleged to have committed, apologetic and persuasive lexical items, the writer's suggestion of what to do but leaving the Committee to give judgment, and other necessary concrete evidences. The briefness of the letter may also suggest that the writer does not know how to write an appeal letter.

3.9. Data Presentation 4: LoA 4

3.9.1. Paras 1 and 2 of LoA 4

*With reference to your letter dated 15th April, 2021.
I write to appeal the judgment of
Analysis of Paras 1 and 2 of LoA 4*

The writer uses an endophoric marker in a false paragraph as his opening paragraph to show the senders that he is fully aware of the letter and has interest in it. The paragraph is said to be false because this is not even a sentence let alone a paragraph. It may be deduced that the writer did not proofread this important letter before sending out or that she was in a hurry to do so.

Paragraph two (2) is also very short and only indicates the writer’s involvement and plea. The major contents of an appeal letter (as earlier stated) are not included in this letter.

3.9.2, Para 3 of LoA 4

It is of note that my Son...appeared before your disciplinary committee on the 14th of April, 2021 and the judgment was delivered same day going by the date of your letter.

3.9.3. Analysis of Para 3 of LoA 4

The opening of this paragraph with an endophoric marker, indicates the writer’s emphasis on the appearance of his son before the disciplinary panel. It indicates the writer’s displeasure to such action, hence an exhibition of an overt attitude marker which is conspicuously captured in the next paragraph.

The writer’s emphatic expression of this paragraph suggests that the sender of this letter might have made a mistake which this writer capitalize on. Letters of this nature should be handled seriously by both the senders and the receivers.

3.9.4. Para 4 of LoA 4

The swiftness and the speed of your investigation and judgment suggest so many things to me:

- i. *Hasty and Poor Investigations*
- ii. *Nigerian Traditional Method of Prosecution before investigation.*
- iii. *Closure against appeal, in a matter of this nature that leads to heavy penalty and consequences of rustication of the whole of one (1) Semester.*
- iv. *Injustice (Miscarriage of Justice)*

3.9.5. Analysis of Para 4 of LoA 4

The overt expression of attitude markers of the writer in his judgmental submissions of Para 4 of LoA 4 is an indication that this is not a letter of appeal rather a critique of the Panel’s decision. This is rather provocative and capable of inducing the latitude of rejection from the SDC members.

3.10. Para 5 of LoA 4

I will like to put it on record that, my son is both innocent and a victim of hasty and poor investigation. Poor investigations, usually leads to miscarriage of justice. If an investigation is defective, the judgment cannot be said to be fair and just.

3.10.1. Analysis of Para5 of LoA 4

The implied application of the attitude markers in the paragraph above renders this highly judgmental and denies the writer the opportunity of being offered the latitude of acceptance by SDC members.

3.11. Para 6 of LoA 4

I am using this medium to appeal to the management to temper Justice with mercy and review the whole matter with deep sense of Accountability and the fear of God knowing fully, well that every Judge of today, shall surely become a defender before the impartial Judge (Almighty God) of the whole universe tomorrow.

3.11.1. Data analysis of Para 6 of LoA 4

The paragraph opens with a self-mention that fails to perform its normal function of true self-involvement. The writer does not own up to any offence, rather, he offers a directive and a threat to the members of SDC. Although the writer might have felt that he has written an appeal letter, it is a complete unveiled engagement attitude capable of bringing forth the latitude of rejection.

3.11.2. Data Presentation 5: LoA 5

3.11.3. Para 1 of LoA 5

Reference to the former letter of appeal dated 28, April 2021 refer:

*Sir, I write to further appeal that the **letter of rustication** given to ... be converted to **letter of suspension** and consider sending him to Center for New life (CNL*

3.11.4. Data of Analysis of Para 1 of LoA 5

This is a second letter of appeal sent by the mother of the offender to the Committee. It shows that the first letter met the latitude of rejection and she further writes another one hoping that it will meet its desired intention. Looking at the letter, it lacks its basic appeal ingredients rather; it offers suggestions to the Committee. This cannot evoke acceptance from the Committee.

3.11.5. Para 2 of LoA 5

Sir, this letter of Appeal supersedes the former letter dated 28th April, 2021

Please Sir, I further plead for leniency, by slashing the period of his punishment.

3.11.6. Data Analysis of Para 2 of LoA 5

The two-line paragraph is not capable of changing the decision of the committee because there is no evidence to concretise why the punishment should be reduced. Although, there is a self-mention and a persuasive expression by the mother of the offender, it is very brief and lacks its basic configurations, therefore it cannot be accepted by the Committee.

4. Findings

From the analysis of the data above, the researcher found the following

- i. Self-mentions and admission of offences are catalysts that propel the Committee to choose the latitude of acceptance, but self-defence accelerates punishments early given and encourages the Committee to sustain punishments (earlier given).
- ii. The use of indirect engagement markers may evoke rejections of appeals as the writer seems to distant himself/herself from the offence he/she has committed.
- i. Appropriate application of engagement makers may induce overt psychological traumas and evoke pity on the readers or listeners.
- ii. Self-induced defense may trigger rejection of appeals.
- iii. Very short letters of appeal are clear marks of lack of seriousness and always evoke the latitude of rejection by any Higher Authority of any institution.
- iv. Writers of appeal letters should be very meticulous so that unnecessary and damaging extraneous materials are not included in the letter.
- v. Inclusion of irrelevant information may evoke misinterpretations of the texts.
- vi. The predominant metadiscourse strategies in letter of appeal are self-mentions (self-involvement strategies); as each letter opens with them, used them in the middle of the letter and sometimes at the end of the letter.
- vii. Grammatical errors and wrong spellings in letters of appeal signal the writer’s unprepared and unserious attitude towards a serious letter of this nature and affect the authorities’ rejection of such plea.
- viii. Some letters of appeal are not properly proofread before they are sent out as evidenced in some paragraphs above.
- ix. Some letters of appeal are not supported with concrete reasons why leniencies should be administered; but full of directives to the Committee; these kinds always receive rejections.
- x. Inclusion of extraneous ideas is useless; it only makes the writing verbose and redundant.
- xi. Lack of evidence to support one’s plea ends up in changing nothings; it only leads to a waste of time and money.

- xii. Most letters of appeals are written by women, this may suggest that they (women) are emotionally traumatic than their husbands. It may also be inferred that their fathers are either busy or late.

Conclusion and recommendations

Letters of appeals are meant to solicit pardon or lessen punishments for offenders. It is therefore regrettable that a lot of letters of appeal sent to SDC lack basic metadiscursive strategies to boost their acceptability; and as such parents and guardians continuously write appeal letters that do not meet their desired goals; rather, SDC keeps sustaining its first decisions (irrespective of how many times such letters are written). Does it mean that once SDC takes its decisions, they are always binding? No, it is the ability of the writer to apply metadiscursive strategies appropriately that determines the outcomes of the judgment of the Committee which are generally based on two latitudes; that of acceptance and rejection.

Self-mentions and self admission of offences should be encouraged in letters of appeals to SDC. Also, basic persuasive lexical items and concrete evidences should be overtly written and presented to the Committee in order to evoke their acceptance; which would be resulted in the said letters achieving their desired intentions. Attitude markers should be completely avoided; rather, writers should be encouraged to employ transactional metadiscourses of self-mentions, boosters, engagement markers and interactive metadiscourse of evidentials appropriately in letters of appeal. If these are properly applied, letters of appeal can readily obtained theirs acceptance by SDC members and simultaneously, the desires of the writers will be granted.

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